

NEXUS BETWEEN READING HABITS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS:
EVIDENCE FROM LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE STUDENTS
AT THE UNIVERSITY OF PESHAWAR, KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA

Eman Afroze¹, Dr Sajjad Ahmad^{*2}, Sami Ullah³, Hamna Azeem⁴, Rameen Iqbal⁵

^{1,4,5}B.S Students, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Peshawar
²Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Peshawar
³M.Phil Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Peshawar

²sajjad_lis74@yahoo.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Dr. Sajjad Ahmad

Abstract

This study explores the reading habits of Library and Information Science (LIS) students at the University of Peshawar and examines how these habits influence their academic achievements. A structured questionnaire was distributed to a stratified random sample of 116 BS and M.Phil students, with 65 valid responses analyzed. Key variables included reading attitude, frequency, types of materials read, and reading purposes. The findings reveal that most students exhibit a positive attitude toward reading and prefer digital resources such as Google Scholar, YouTube, and e-books over traditional printed materials. Although reading frequency varied, students who read more frequently, both academic and non-academic materials, tended to perform better academically, as evidenced by a weak but statistically significant positive correlation with CGPA. The study also found no significant gender-based differences in reading habits. Students reported reading for a variety of purposes, including academic success, professional development, language improvement, and staying informed. The research highlights the importance of fostering consistent, purposeful reading habits among LIS students. The study recommends integrating digital literacy skills, expanding access to electronic resources, and designing reading-based activities within academic programs to support student performance and lifelong learning.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Reading remains a vital part of education as a key way for people to communicate in a society with high literacy. Fidzani (1998) emphasized that books still

play a major role in our lives today. Despite the rise of audio-visual media, traditional books continue to be the most important source of knowledge and information. Gaining more knowledge through

reading helps individuals feel more confident when presenting themselves. Reading habits represent a structured and intentional method of study that students consistently apply to grasp academic topics and succeed in exams. Students' academic success is significantly influenced by their reading habits (Owusu-Acheaw Larson, 2014).

Reading and academic success are interconnected and rely on one another. Students frequently originate from various backgrounds and regions, possessing differing degrees of academic success. Consequently, their reading habits exhibit distinct patterns. Although certain students display positive reading habits, others tend to show negative reading habits. Academic achievement refers to the extent of knowledge an individual has gained from educational institutions (Bashir & Mattoo, 2012). Reading practices have been identified to significantly influence the academic performance of students (Cunningham & Stanovovich, 2001; Hangu, et al., 2014; Levine, Waite & Bowman, 2007). It is a crucial approach to gaining knowledge and is vital for advanced academic achievement (Bashir & Mattoo, 2012), and it influences the success of university students worldwide. Students interested in reading, Students who are not enrolled in course 1490 (Balan, Katenga, & Simon, 2019) still gain from reading academic literature. This type of reading helps improve both their emotional and academic skills. Research by (Okwilagwe, 1998) shows that engaging with scholarly texts benefits all students, regardless of whether they are part of the course. It enhances their ability to understand complex ideas and develop emotional awareness. This suggests that academic literature offers valuable benefits beyond the classroom setting. It supports students' overall growth and learning.

When students have strong reading habits, they can enhance their critical thinking abilities and ultimately achieve improved academic results. Furthermore, reading non-academic literature also improves students' language abilities (Balan, Katenga & Simon, 2019), Palani (2012) states that the habit of reading is a crucial and vital element for fostering a literate society globally. It influences individuals' personalities, aids them in developing effective thinking strategies, and generates innovative concepts. Nevertheless, advancements in Mass Media

have persisted in affecting the interest in reading (physical copies of literature like...) books, magazines, and journals, among other forms.

Palani (2012) also believes that effective reading is a crucial pathway to effective learning, with reading being interconnected to the overall educational process; therefore, achieving educational success necessitates the development of successful reading habits. He thinks that reading involves recognizing symbols and linking them to the correct meanings. It necessitates recognition and understanding. Understanding skills enable the student to grasp the significance of words both alone and within context. Prior to the arrival of television, both youths and adults had ample time to engage in reading. Besides educators, other professionals used to spend their free time reading literature in both English and local languages. English medium schools typically required additional reading from their students. However, all of these have turned into a memory. She stated that today, the habit of reading has diminished in value as people of all ages are captivated by television. Regarding educational institutions, preparing students for exams appears to be the paramount focus of our education system (Owusu-Acheaw Larson, 2014).

Reading and academic success are crucial for researchers and educators to understand that each child, whether gifted, average, typical, or struggling, should be taught in a manner suited to their needs; however, if they have effective study habits, they can excel in academics and in various circumstances. The reading habits assist the learner in acquiring valuable and significant knowledge. Effective reading habits serve as a powerful tool for students to succeed in life (Bashir & Mattoo, 2012). In this study, "Reading Habits" is assessed through reading attitude, frequency of reading, kinds of materials read, and reasons for reading.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Reading habits play a crucial role in academic success, particularly for students of Library and Information Science (LIS), where extensive reading is essential for knowledge acquisition and professional competence. However, with the increasing influence of digital media, changing study patterns, and diverse information sources, students' reading habits may be

shifting, potentially affecting their academic performance. In the context of the University of Peshawar, little research has been conducted to assess the reading behaviors of LIS students and how these habits influence their academic achievements.

This study aims to investigate the reading habits of LIS students at the University of Peshawar, examining factors such as reading frequency, preferred reading materials, and the impact of digital resources. Additionally, it seeks to determine the relationship between students' reading habits and their academic performance, identifying potential challenges and proposing strategies to enhance their reading culture.

1.3 Objectives

The following are the objectives of this study:

1. To explore the attitude of library and information science students toward reading.
2. To assess the reading frequency of library and information science students.
3. To identify the preferred types of reading materials among library and information science students.
4. To determine the purposes of reading for students studying library and information science.
5. To examine the influence of reading frequency on the academic performance of LIS students.

1.4 Literature Review

1.4.1 Understanding Reading and Reading Habits

Reading is more than just a basic skill; it is a way to gain knowledge, improve thinking, and grow academically. According to (Palani, 2012) reading is a valuable activity that helps individuals stay informed and educated. Reading habits refer to how often, how long, and what kind of materials people read. These habits vary from person to person, depending on their interests, access to resources, and environment.

Researchers like (Chettri, 2013) found that students who develop good reading habits early tend to perform better in their academic life. Reading habits include reading newspapers, magazines, books, journals, and even digital content like blogs and e-books.

1.4.2 Reading Habits in Academic Life

Reading plays a very important role in education. Students who read regularly often improve their

vocabulary, writing skills, and general knowledge. A study by (Owusu-Acheaw, 2014) in Ghana found a positive link between students' reading habits and their academic performance. They discovered that students who made reading a regular part of their daily routine scored higher in exams compared to those who didn't.

Similarly, (Pandian, 2000) emphasized that reading habits are directly connected to academic success and personal development. He pointed out that students with strong reading habits are usually more confident and perform better in class discussions and writing assignments.

1.4.3 Reading Habits and Their Relationship with Academic Success

Reading is one of the most important skills for students. It not only helps them to understand their course materials better but also improves their language skills, vocabulary, and ability to think critically. Over the years, many researchers have studied the connection between students' reading habits and their academic success. Most of these studies have found a positive relationship students who read more tend to do better in their academic work. Saeed and Ghazal (2018) conducted research to explore the reading habits of university students in Lahore and their effect on their academic achievement. The study was driven by concerns that, although educational resources are becoming more accessible, students are not effectively using reading to enhance their academic performance.

In addition to reading habits, various factors play a crucial role in shaping students' academic achievements. Notable among these are teaching strategies and quality (Blazar, 2015; Ganyaupfu, 2013), the support from peers (Smithikrai et al., 2018), family background (Mushtaq & Khan, 2012), and attendance in classes (Hocking, 2008). Research indicates that student-centered learning methods tend to yield superior academic outcomes in comparison to traditional teacher-centered approaches (Tynjälä, Välimaa & Sarja, 1998).

1.4.4 Reading and Its Effects on Academic Performance

Khan and Ahmad (2017) conducted a study to explore the relationship between reading habits and academic

performance among university students in Islamabad, Pakistan. The research focused on undergraduate students from different faculties, including social sciences, natural sciences, and management. The main objective was to understand whether students who regularly read both academic and non-academic materials performed better in their university exams compared to those who did not read often. The study revealed a positive correlation between reading habits and academic performance. Students who read regularly especially those who read academic books and supplementary materials had higher GPAs, stronger critical thinking skills, and better class participation. Interestingly, students who balanced their academic reading with non-academic reading (e.g., Urdu novels, English fiction, and newspapers) showed enhanced vocabulary, improved writing expression, and greater confidence in presentations. The researchers found that most students preferred digital reading (PDF books, online articles, blogs), but a significant number of students still enjoyed reading printed books. The majority of high-performing students spent at least one hour daily reading outside class assignments. The study also identified common challenges faced by Pakistani university students: Lack of access to libraries or up-to-date books, Time constraints due to part-time jobs or family responsibilities and so on.

Owusu-Acheaw and Larson (2014) conducted a major study at Koforidua Polytechnic in Ghana to investigate how students' reading habits affected their academic performance. The aim of the study was to understand if there was a direct relationship between students' frequency of reading and their academic success. The researchers used a quantitative research approach, collecting data through structured questionnaires. The study revealed a positive and significant relationship between reading habits and academic performance. Students who read regularly especially those who read daily for 30 minutes or more had higher GPAs compared to students who rarely read. Among the materials read, academic books and lecture notes were the most positively linked to academic success. Those who read for academic purposes scored better in exams than those who mostly read for entertainment. One interesting finding was that about 40% of the students preferred digital reading, using e-books and online articles.

Issa, Aliyu, Akangbe, and Adedeji (2012) carried out a detailed study in Ogun State, Nigeria, focusing on how secondary school students' reading habits impacted their academic performance. The researchers used a mixed-method approach, combining both surveys and interviews. The study included 180 students from selected public and private secondary schools. Data was collected through structured questionnaires, which asked students how often they read, the kinds of reading materials they preferred, and what times of day they read. Interviews were also conducted with teachers and parents to gain deeper insight into how students were encouraged (or discouraged) to read. The results of the study showed that students who read daily or at least 3-4 times per week performed significantly better in their academic subjects. Another major finding was that students who had strong support from parents and teachers were more likely to develop good reading habits.

Annamalai and Muniandy (2013) conducted a study to explore the connection between students' attitudes toward reading and their academic performance in Malaysian polytechnics. The study found a strong positive relationship between reading habits and academic performance. Students who had a positive attitude toward reading, regardless of whether they were reading academic or non-academic materials, scored higher GPAs compared to students who read less or disliked reading. Interestingly, students who mixed both academic and non-academic reading showed better critical thinking and overall learning skills than students who read only textbooks.

Saeed and Ghazal (2018) carried out a study to examine the reading habits of university students in Lahore and how these habits influenced their academic performance. The researchers wanted to understand students' attitudes toward reading, the frequency and type of materials read, and the impact on their exam performance. The study involved 250 undergraduate students from three major universities in Lahore: University of the Punjab, Lahore College for Women University (LCWU), and University of Management and Technology (UMT). The results showed that students who read regularly both academic and leisure materials tended to have higher GPAs than those who only read textbooks close to exams. About 68% of high-performing students reported that they read daily for at least 45 minutes.

They also read materials beyond the syllabus, including novels, newspapers, and online research articles. Interestingly, the study found that students who read in both English and Urdu had a broader vocabulary and stronger writing skills. Those who read only in one language, especially under pressure to meet academic requirements, had weaker comprehension and were more anxious during assessments. Another important finding was the impact of reading environment. Students who had access to quiet spaces like hostel study rooms or campus libraries performed better than those who read in noisy home settings.

Multiple studies reviewed in this chapter, such as those by Owusu-Acheaw and Larson (2014), Issa et al. (2012), Annamalai and Muniandy (2013), and others, have consistently shown that students who read more frequently have higher Grade Point Averages (GPA), better exam scores, and more academic confidence. The benefits of reading extend beyond academic performance it also boosts students' ability to express them, solve problems, and engage in class discussions. These are essential skills in higher education, especially for students in disciplines like Library and Information Science (LIS), where reading and information analysis are core competencies.

Furthermore, studies from Pakistan, such as those by Khan & Ahmad (2017) and Saeed and Ghazal (2018), confirm that the same positive patterns exist in local academic environments. These studies also highlight unique challenges faced by Pakistani students, including limited access to quality reading resources, digital distractions, lack of motivation, and underdeveloped library systems. Despite these barriers, students who manage to maintain consistent reading routines, especially those supported by good reading environments and guidance from teachers and parents, are more likely to succeed academically. In the specific context of Peshawar, recent research (e.g., Adnan Ullah et al., 2024) has shown that students benefit from both print and digital reading formats. A balanced use of both can lead to better comprehension and retention. However, it also points to the need for universities to invest in improving reading facilities, digital access, and awareness programs to foster reading as a daily habit.

Therefore, the conclusion that can be drawn from the literature is that reading is not only a basic academic

skill but also a powerful tool for student success. Institutions of higher learning, particularly in Pakistan, should recognize the critical role of reading habits in improving academic achievement. This can be done by promoting reading-friendly environments, integrating reading into academic programs, enhancing library resources, encouraging reading for pleasure, and training students in time management and reading strategies. By doing so, universities can help their students become more informed, skilled, and academically successful individuals who are better prepared for the demands of professional life.

1.5 Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research approach, employing a descriptive survey method to explore the reading habits of Library and Information Science (LIS) students and analyzed their relationship with academic achievements of the LIS students. A study strategy was utilized to provide an in-depth understanding of the issue within a single institutional context—the University of Peshawar.

1.5.1 Population

The total population in this study consists of BS and M.Phil students enrolled in different semesters. The total no of students enrolled in BS semester 2 is 15, semester 4 is 31, semester 6 is 40 and semester 8 is 34 and the number of M.Phil is 46 enrolled in various semesters, so the total no of population of this study became 164.

1.5.2 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The research sample comprised 116 participants, drawn from an overall population of 164 students, with the help of Rao-Soft sample size calculator, with a confidence level of 95%. The population was split into two groups: BS and M.Phil students. Out of 118 participants in the BS group, 83 were included, and from 46 M.Phil students, 33 were included. A stratified random sampling method was used to guarantee representation from both educational levels, leading to more precise and generalizable results across the various strata's based on qualification level. The details are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Sample Size Detail

S.No	Strata	No. of Population	No. of Sample
01	B.S	118	83
02	M.Phil	46	33
Total		164	116

1.5.3 Development and Descriptions of Data Collection Instrument

The first draft of the questionnaire was developed with the help of previous literature. The survey questionnaire was designed to draw all the important information from the students according to the objectives of this study. Students were asked to indicate, on the 5-point Likert scale, their reading attitude, reading frequency, materials read, and the purpose of their reading. Data collection instrument included demographic information such as gender, age, academic year and GPA in the semester cleared.

The questionnaire contained two parts. Section-A dealt with demographics; Section-B asked students questions about Reading attitude, Reading frequency, Reading materials and Reading purposes. The description of the data collection instrument is provided in Table 2.

Table 2

Description of Data Collection Instrument

Parts	Variable	No of Items
Section A	Demographics	4
Section B	Reading attitude	9
	Reading frequency	8
	Reading materials	8
	Reading purposes	8

1.5.4 Reliability Analysis of the Data Collection Tool

Reliability denotes the overall consistency of a scale. Using the relationships between its items, it assesses whether the items on the scale align with one another and signify a singular dimension, construct, or area of interest (Salkind, 2011). Cronbach's alpha (1951) was utilized to evaluate the internal consistency of the overall scale measuring ICT acceptability and utility, along with its individual sub-clusters, as it is a well-known method commonly used to determine internal consistency and reliability (Khan, Rehman & Rehman, 2013). Cronbach's alpha has a value that varies between 0 and 1. As the score approaches one, the instrument becomes more dependable; when it nears zero, the instrument is less dependable (Erfanmanesh, Abrizah & Karim, 2012). The Cronbach's alpha (CA) value for this multi-item instrument was computed using SPSS version 22. Table 3 shows the Cronbach's alpha (CA) value for the instrument, demonstrating that the scale is very reliable for application on students.

Table 3

Reliability of the Data Collection Tool

No	Scale	No. of items	CA Values
01	Reading attitude	09	.795
02	Reading frequency	08	.821
03	Types of materials read	08	.726
04	Reading purpose	08	.853
05	Overall Scale	33	.927

1.5.5 Procedure for Data Collection and Data Analysis

In this study, data was collected through a structured questionnaire. For this purpose 116 questionnaires were shared among the respondents selected randomly through Lottery method. Among which 33 were distributed among M.Phil and 83 were distributed among BS students. Out of those only sixty five (65) responses were received. Descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation were employed to examine the replies. These made it easier to comprehend the typical answers and the degree of variation among individuals. SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) was used to conduct the analysis. The required statistics such as frequencies, percentages, Mean scores etc. were used to analyze the data and reach the findings.

1.6 Major Findings**1.6.1 Data Screening and Response Rate**

A total of 116 questionnaires were distributed among students across various academic programs, including

33 M.Phil students and 83 BS students. Before the data analysis, the questionnaires returned i.e. 65 were checked for completeness and correctness and entered into SPSS for further analysis, leaving the response rate to 56%.

1.6.2 Demographic Information of Respondents

The demographic data collected included gender, the age of respondents, the program of study they are enrolled in, and their CGPA. Their further details are provided as under:

1.6.3 Gender-wise Distribution

In order to determine the gender distribution among the sample, one of the demographic questions asked about the participants' genders. The results are displayed in Table 4, which reveals that the majority of respondents (55.4%) were men and 44.6% were women.

Table 4

Gender-wise Distribution of the respondents (N=65)

S No	Gender	Percentage	Frequency
01	Male	55.4	36
02	Female	44.6	29
Total		100%	65

4.2.2 Age-wise distribution

The demographic part included an additional question designed to investigate the respondents' age distribution. The largest group of participants (47.7%) was between the ages of 22 and 25, followed by those between the ages of 18 and 21 (38.5%), as seen in Table 5. Just 3.1% of the respondents were older than 31, while a smaller percentage (10.8%) were between the ages of 26 and 30.

Table 5

Age-Wise Distribution of the respondents (N=65)

S No	Age	Percentage	Frequency
01	18-21	38.5	25
02	22-25	47.7	31
03	26-30	10.8	7
04	31 and above	3.1	2
Total		100%	65

4.2.3 Program of the Study-wise Distribution

The purpose of this component of the demographic data was to determine which academic program the respondents were enrolled in. The bulk of participants (76.9%) were enrolled in the BS program, with the remaining 23.1% coming from the MS/M.Phil program, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6

Program of the study wise distribution of the respondents (N=65)

S No	Program	Percentage	Frequency
01	BS	76.9	50
02	MS/M.Phil	23.1	15
Total		100%	65

4.2.4 CGPA-wise distribution

To learn more about the respondents' academic performance, the CGPA distribution was also examined. The majority of respondents (64.6%) had a CGPA between 3.00 and 3.49, whereas 21.5% had a CGPA between 3.50 and 4.00, as seen in Table 7. None of the participants reported a CGPA between 2.00 and 2.49, but a lesser percentage (13.8%) got a CGPA between 2.50 and 2.99.

Table 7

CGPA-Wise Distribution of the respondents (N=65)

S No	CGPA	Percentage	Frequency
01	2.00-2.49	0	0
02	2.50-2.99	13.8	9

03	3.00-4.00	64.6	42
04	3.50-4.00	21.5	14
Total		100%	65

4.3 Descriptive Statistics for Reading Attitude

Table 8 displays students’ perspectives on reading attitude based on nine statements evaluated using a five-point Likert scale. The information indicates an overall favorable attitude toward reading with a mean score of 3.69 (SD=.751), especially regarding its educational significance. Further analysis of the scale items shows that a considerable number of students affirm that reading improves understanding during homework (66.2% agree or strongly agree), and a vast majority (78.4%) think that reading fosters critical thinking skills. These items obtained some of the highest average scores, with 3.83 and 4.15 respectively, reflecting strong consensus. Moreover, 72.3% of learners believe that their reading practices enhance academic success (mean = 3.85), and 69.2% prefer reading in calm surroundings to improve focus (mean = 3.78). A comparable percentage (70.7%) recognizes that reading is significant in their daily activities, emphasizing the vital role reading has in their academic and personal spheres.

Nonetheless, the information also shows a varied preference for learning methods. Although 50.7% of students expressed a preference for watching videos rather than reading for learning, the mean score of 3.31 indicates a mixed opinion. Moreover, 47.7% of students indicated they read solely when required for assignments or exams, suggesting a rather practical attitude towards reading within a part of the group. Notably, perspectives on reading academic books are more diverse. While 69.2% concur or strongly concur that they enjoy reading scholarly books, 21.5% firmly disagree, indicating a divided opinion on conventional academic materials. The results suggest that although students acknowledge the importance of reading for understanding, analytical thinking, and educational achievement, different learning approaches such as videos are favored too, and the desire to read scholarly materials differs among people.

Table 8
Descriptive Statistics of Reading Attitude (N=65)

No	Statements	SD%	D%	N%	A%	SA%	Mean%	SD%
1	I like to read academic books.	21.5	1.5	7.7	47.7	21.5	3.46	1.426
2	Reading plays a significant role in my everyday activities.	6.2	9.2	13.8	41.5	29.2	3.78	1.152
3	I like watching videos more than reading when learning.	15.4	10.8	23.1	29.2	21.5	3.31	1.345
4	I only read when it’s required for homework or tests.	7.7	21.5	23.1	30.8	16.9	3.28	1.206
5	Reading improves my comprehension when doing homework.	4.6	4.6	24.6	35.4	30.8	3.83	1.069

6	I believe that reading can help me develop my critical thinking abilities.	4.6	3.1	13.8	29.2	49.2	4.15	1.079
7	I enjoy reading in a peaceful environment to improve focus.	10.8	6.2	13.8	32.3	36.9	3.78	1.305
8	My personal reading habits play a crucial role in my academic achievement.	9.2	6.2	13.3	35.4	36.9	3.85	1.253
9	I watch and learn from videos and audios.	3.1	12.3	16.9	38.5	29.2	3.78	1.097
10	Overall reading attitude						3.69	.751

4.3.1 Independent Sample T-Test Results for Reading Attitude

An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare overall rating of RA (Over all RA) scores between males and females. There was no significant difference in scores for males (M = 3.61, SD = 0.83) and females (M = 3.80, SD = 0.64); $t(63) = -1.01, p = .318$ (two-tailed), 95% CI [-0.56, 0.19]. Levene’s test for equality of variances was not significant, $F(1, 63) = 3.90, p = .053$, indicating that the assumption of equal variances was met.

4.4 Descriptive Statistics for Reading Frequency

Table 9 offers details on how often students participate in various reading activities, especially academic and general reading, along with the overall reading frequency. The data indicates an overall favorable reading frequency among the LIS students with a mean score of 3.57 (SD=.787), the information indicates that digital reading is the most common activity for students, with 75.4% reporting they read via digital platforms such as e-books or online journals multiple times each week. This statement achieved the highest average score (3.85), suggesting a robust inclination towards digital formats, probably because of their convenience and accessibility. It is also typical for students to read for assignments or presentations, with 60% participating in it at least once or twice

weekly (mean = 3.58). Likewise, studying for exams (63%) and obtaining academic information via professional sites such as Research Gate or LinkedIn (61.5%) are quite common activities, each with an average of 3.63. These findings indicate that students are effectively employing reading as a strategic resource for achieving academic success, particularly during times of academic pressure.

Notably, general (non-academic) reading during leisure time also performs strongly, as 66.1% of students partake in this activity weekly or more often (mean = 3.62), suggesting that recreational reading continues to be an essential aspect of their reading habits. Nonetheless, the regularity of reading academic and textbook materials is lower, with merely 46.2% of students engaging in this activity daily or multiple times a week. This item has the smallest average score (3.14), implying that continuous reading of textbooks may not be a regular practice for many. In summary, although students often participate in multiple types of academic reading—especially digital and goal-oriented reading—their consistent interaction with essential academic materials such as textbooks is relatively reduced. The results indicate a transition towards digital and focused reading habits that correspond with academic responsibilities and time limitations, showcasing evolving reading practices in the digital era.

Table 9
Reading frequency of LIS Students (N=65)

No	Statements	SD%	D%	N%	A%	SA%	Mean%	SD%
1	I read academic and textbooks on a regular basis (e.g., daily or several times a week).	16.9	9.2	27.7	35.4	10.8	3.14	1.248
2	I read materials for preparing assignments or presentations at least once or twice a week.	7.7	4.6	27.7	41.5	18.5	3.58	1.088
3	I read general (non-academic) books during my free time (e.g., once a week or more).	12.3	9.2	12.3	36.9	29.2	3.62	1.331
4	I read using digital platforms like e-books or online journals several times a week.	4.6	7.7	12.3	49.2	26.2	3.85	1.049
5	I read academic content on professional platforms like Research Gate or LinkedIn weekly.	6.2	13.8	18.5	33.8	27.7	3.63	1.206
6	I read printed journal articles at least once or twice a week.	7.7	9.2	23.1	32.3	27.7	3.63	1.206
7	I read materials specifically for test preparation regularly (e.g., during exam periods or weekly).	6.2	9.2	21.5	41.5	21.5	3.63	1.112
8	I read academic publications, research papers, or scholarly books multiple times a week.	7.7	10.8	27.7	30.8	23.1	3.51	1.187
9	Overall reading frequency						3.57	.787

4.4.1 Independent Sample T-Test Results for Reading Frequency

An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare overall reading frequency scores between male and female students. The results showed that the difference was not statistically significant: $t(63) = -0.75$, $p = .455$ (two-tailed), $d = 0.18$. Male students ($M = 3.51$, $SD = 0.81$) reported slightly lower reading frequency than female students ($M = 3.66$, $SD = 0.77$), but this difference was not statistically significant. Levene’s Test for Equality of Variances was not

significant ($F = 0.045$, $p = .832$), so equal variances were assumed.

4.5 Descriptive Statistics for Materials Read

Table 10 examines the various types of reading materials that students engage with, as well as their preferences for different formats and sources. The data indicates an overall materials read score by LIS students with a mean score of 3.56 ($SD=.735$), It shows that LIS students generally engage in reading of various type of materials. Moreover, the findings indicate a significant inclination towards digital and

online resources, with platforms such as Facebook and YouTube recognized as valuable academic sources by a notable 72.3% of respondents (A% and SA% combined). This particular item also boasts the highest mean score of 3.88, implying that students are increasingly depending on multimedia and social platforms to obtain academic content. Similarly, Google Scholar is favored over conventional academic databases by 72.3% of students, achieving a commendable mean of 3.78, which reinforces the trend towards accessible and user-friendly online research tools. Nevertheless, academic databases like JSTOR and ProQuest are still utilized by a considerable number of students, with 60% indicating regular usage (mean = 3.49), although they are not as strongly preferred as Google Scholar.

Regarding reading formats, the results reveal varied preferences. Approximately 53.8% of students express a preference for physical books over digital formats; however, the presence of 23.1% neutral and 23.1% disagreeing responses (SD% + D%) results in a moderate mean of 3.39 for this statement. This

indicates that while a significant portion still favors physical books, digital reading is becoming increasingly prevalent. Supporting this trend, 63.1% of students report engaging with online platforms such as blogs and e-books (mean = 3.51), demonstrating a widespread adoption of digital reading habits. Interestingly, reading textbooks remains a priority for many students, with 60% stating that they dedicate more time to reading textbooks than any other type of material (mean = 3.65), underscoring the significance of core academic texts despite the growing prominence of online sources. Conversely, storybooks seem to be read less frequently, with only 50% of students agreeing or strongly agreeing to reading them (mean = 3.43), indicating a potential decline in recreational reading among certain individuals. In summary, the data illustrates a diverse and evolving reading landscape among students. While traditional materials such as textbooks and physical books remain relevant, the rise of digital resources is evident.

Table 10
Descriptive statistics about Materials Read (N=65)

No	Statements	SD%	D%	N%	A%	SA%	Mean%	SD%
1	I prefer reading physical books over digital formats.	16.9	6.2	23.1	29.2	24.6	3.39	1.377
2	I read newspapers and magazines in print form.	10.8	16.9	16.9	35.4	20.0	3.37	1.282
3	I read storybooks.	15.4	12.3	12.3	3.8	26.2	3.43	1.403
4	I read using online plate forms such as blogs and e-books.	7.7	9.2	20.0	50.8	12.3	3.51	1.077
5	I spend more time reading Textbooks than any other material.	7.7	10.8	21.5	29.2	30.8	3.65	1.243
6	I regularly use information sources available on internet databases like JSTOR and Pro Quest etc.	12.3	10.8	16.9	35.4	24.6	3.49	1.312
7	I prefer using Google Scholar to find information than academic databases.	10.8	4.6	12.3	40.0	32.3	3.78	1.258

8	Facebook and YouTube videos help me find useful academic reading materials and resources.	3.1	9.2	15.4	41.5	30.8	3.88	1.053
9	Overall materials read						3.56	.735

4.5.1 Independent Sample T-Test Results for Materials Read

An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare scores on reading material usage (over all MR) between male and female students. The results indicated that the difference was not statistically significant, but it approached significance at the 0.05 level:

$t(63) = -1.53, p = .131$ (two-tailed), $d = 0.38$. Female students ($M = 3.72, SD = 0.73$) scored slightly higher than male students ($M = 3.44, SD = 0.73$) on material read. However, this difference was not statistically significant. Levene’s Test for Equality of Variances was not significant ($F = 0.024, p = .876$), so equal variances were assumed.

4.6 Descriptive Statistics for Purpose of Reading

Table 11 shows why students read, highlighting a mix of academic, career, and personal reasons. The top reason is to improve language and communication skills, with 75.4% of students agreeing or strongly agreeing. The average rating for this reason is 3.94, making it the most common purpose. This suggests that students understand how reading boosts their language ability. Developing research skills is also a key reason, with 69.3% of students responding positively and a mean of 3.85. Many students read to understand their field better, which received a mean score of 3.80 and was supported by 70.2% of respondents. These responses show that students read not just for class, but for wider academic growth and learning. Gaining professional skills was also important. About 66.1% of students read for career-related reasons, with a mean of 3.80. This indicates that many students see reading as essential for future

jobs. Additionally, 61.6% of students read to stay updated on current events and trends, with an average of 3.68. This reflects their wish to stay socially and intellectually informed.

Interest in exploring new ideas and trends is another major motivation. Sixty-one percent of students agree with this reason, with a mean score of 3.71. Their curiosity drives them to read beyond academic tasks. On the other hand, reading outside coursework scored slightly lower. Only 55.4% of students agree, with an average of 3.49. This suggests that while students are open to reading for fun or personal interest, it is not their main focus. Reading for academic success was less common. Only 56.9% of students agreed or strongly agreed, with a mean score of 3.38. About 20% disagreed, showing that not all students see success as their main reason for reading. Some prioritize other goals more strongly.

Overall, the results show that students read for many reasons: Academic and career goals are strong motivators. They also read for personal growth, skill-building, and staying aware of societal changes. These diverse motivations shape how and why students choose to read. In addition to that the data indicates an overall purpose of reading among LIS students with a mean score of 3.70 ($SD=.778$). Indicating an overall positive and reasonably elevated degree of enthusiasm for reading. This indicates that many students participate in reading not only as a school obligation but also for wider educational and personal growth aims. The comparatively small standard deviation suggests that the participants’ responses were quite uniform, reflecting a common view on the significance of reading. These results emphasize the importance of reading as a significant academic and intellectual pursuit for LIS students

Table 11
Descriptive Statistics of Purpose of Reading (N=65)

No	Statements	SD%	D%	N%	A%	SA%	Mean%	SD%
1	My main motivation for reading is academic success.	13.8	6.2	23.1	41.5	15.4	3.38	1.234
2	I read to learn things apart from my coursework.	4.6	12.3	27.7	40.0	15.4	3.49	1.048
3	I read to explore new ideas and trends.	1.5	13.8	23.1	35.4	26.2	3.71	1.057
4	I read for developing my research skills.	3.1	9.2	18.5	38.5	30.8	3.85	1.064
5	I read to be informed about current events and trends.	6.2	6.2	29.2	30.8	27.7	3.68	1.133
6	I read to improve my language and communication skills.	7.7	3.1	13.8	38.5	36.9	3.94	1.158
7	I read to develop professional skills beneficial for my career.	1.5	12.3	20.0	36.9	29.2	3.80	1.049
8	I read in order to gain a deeper understanding of my discipline.	7.7	31.1	18.5	43.1	27.1	3.80	1.121
9	Overall purpose of reading						3.70	.778

4.6.1 Independent Sample T-Test Results for Purpose of Reading

An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare the purpose of reading scores between male and female students. The results showed that the difference was not statistically significant: $t(63) = -0.65$, $p = .519$ (two-tailed), $d = 0.16$. Female students ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.77$) had slightly higher mean scores for reading purpose than male students ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 0.79$), but the difference was small and not statistically meaningful. Levene's test for equality of variances was not significant ($F = 0.199$, $p = .657$), indicating that the assumption of equal variances was met.

4.7 The Relationship of Reading Frequency on the Academic Performance of LIS Students

A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between the frequency of reading (overall RF) and academic performance (CGPA) among Library and Information Science (LIS) students. The results indicated a positive and statistically significant correlation, $r(63) = .27$, $p = .029$, suggesting that students who reported reading more frequently tended to achieve higher CGPAs. Although the strength of the correlation is relatively weak, the finding is meaningful, as it highlights a potential link between consistent reading habits and academic success in this student population.

4.8 Discussion

This study offers important insights into how Library and Information Science (LIS) students read, their attitudes, and their preferences. It also explores how these factors relate to their academic work. Overall, the findings show that LIS students generally have a positive view of reading. They participate in a variety of reading activities and are motivated by both academic and personal reasons.

A key result is the strong positive attitude towards reading. Most students agree that reading enhances critical thinking (average score = 4.15) and helps with academic success (average = 3.85). This aligns with earlier studies literature (Balan, Katenga & Simon, 2019), that highlight the mental and academic benefits of regular reading. Despite their good attitude, some students adopt a practical approach, reading mainly when exams or assignments require it. This suggests they value reading but may not read regularly for pleasure or habit. When it comes to reading habits, the data shows that students frequently use digital content and read mainly for school tasks. They most often read on digital platforms (average = 3.85) and for assignments or tests (averages between 3.58 and 3.63). This points to a shift toward goal-driven, online reading habits. However, reading textbooks regularly scored the lowest (average = 3.14). This may reflect a lack of interest or limited time. Previous research literature (Balan, Katenga, & Simon, 2019), confirms that more frequent reading is linked to better thinking skills and academic results.

The study's details about reading material match these trends, with social media sites like Facebook and YouTube (average = 3.88) and Google Scholar (average = 3.78) being popular resources. While students still use print books, most prefer easily accessible online sources. This shift (Balan, Katenga, & Simon, 2019), shows how students are changing their reading habits to match the convenience of digital tools (Ismail, Ahmad & Ahmad, 2013). Students see reading mainly as a way to improve skills, especially language, communication, research, and understanding of their field. Their top reason is to develop skills (averages from 3.80 to 3.94). They also mention academic success (average = 3.38), but it is not the main motivation. This suggests students view reading as a tool for growth, not just grades. (Balan, Katenga, & Simon, 2019). The study found no major

differences between male and female students in their attitudes, how often they read, the materials they use, or why they read. Both genders share similar habits and goals. Slight differences exist, with females scoring a bit higher on some measures, but these are not statistically meaningful. Finally, the study shows a small but meaningful link between how often students read and their GPA. The correlation coefficient ($r = .27$, $p = .029$) confirms that students who read more tend to do better academically. While the link is weak, it highlights the value of regular reading for academic success.

5.3 Conclusion

This study examined the reading habits, attitudes, types of materials, and purposes among Library and Information Science students. It also looked at how these habits relate to academic success. Several key points emerge from the findings.

First, LIS students generally hold a positive view of reading, especially when it comes to learning and thinking skills. They see reading as useful for understanding concepts, developing critical thinking, and doing well in school. However, their reading tends to be goal-driven. They tend to read more during exams or when preparing assignments. This suggests that outside of academic tasks, reading may not be a regular activity for most students. A major trend is the shift toward digital reading. Students frequently use e-books, online journals, Google Scholar, social media like Facebook, and video sites like YouTube. These platforms are preferred because they are easy to access and provide information instantly. This change shows how reading habits are changing among students and has important lessons for LIS programs. Schools need to improve digital literacy so students can find, judge, and use online information carefully and responsibly.

Regarding materials, students read from many sources. These include textbooks, research papers, blogs, and online media. While printed books still matter, digital media and multimedia resources are becoming more common. This trend calls for libraries and teachers to expand digital collections and help students learn how to use online databases and resources effectively. Students read for many reasons. Their motivations include improving skills, preparing for careers, and personal growth. Many read to

enhance their language abilities, research skills, and stay informed. This shows that reading plays a broad role in their academic and personal lives, not just for coursework alone. The study found no major difference in reading habits or attitudes between male and female students. Both groups show similar reading behavior. However, there is a small, positive link between how often students read and their GPA. Students who read more tend to do better academically. This suggests that reading is an important part of success in school.

Overall, the results stress the need to support steady, meaningful reading habits for LIS students. Teachers and departments should create activities like reading groups or assignments that encourage regular reading. These efforts should include all students, respecting their different interests and learning styles. The goal is to keep students engaged with reading throughout their studies, especially in a world where digital tools are everywhere. In conclusion, the study shows how reading habits are changing and highlights the importance of encouraging consistent reading. Students benefit from a variety of reading experiences, both print and digital, to support their academic growth and personal development.

5.4 Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. LIS programs should include clear, step-by-step reading tasks such as reading logs, review assignments, and weekly reflections to encourage regular reading.
2. Students should form reading groups or book clubs to enjoy reading for fun and learning outside class. These groups can help develop a strong reading culture and foster peer support.
3. As students depend heavily on online sources like Google Scholar, YouTube, and social media for research, workshops should be conducted to help them identify reliable sources and learn to use academic databases effectively. Workshops or modules should teach students how to manage their time and stay disciplined with independent reading, especially during periods without exams.
4. Libraries should increase access to e-books, online journals, and research databases. Librarians should also offer orientation sessions and guides to help LIS students navigate these resources.

5. Teachers should create courses that include both written content and multimedia, such as videos, info graphics, and podcasts. This approach caters to different learning styles and preferences.

6. Departments can run reading contests or give awards and certificates to students who read actively. This can motivate students to read more voluntarily and reward their consistent effort.

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